

A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY TO ASSESS THE PREVALENCE OF BULLYING AND ITS IMPACT ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMONG SENIOR SECONDARY STUDENTS IN KHALSA COLLEGE PUBLIC SCHOOL, AMRITSAR, PUNJAB.

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Abstract: School children are emerging as creative persons who are preparing for their future role in society. Bullying problems can become so troublesome when interfere with emotional, social, and intellectual development of children. Teachers are in better position to detect the sign and symptoms of common bullying problems in the school setting. The present study aimed to assess the prevalence of bullying at its impact on academic performance among senior secondary students in Khalsa College Public School, Amritsar, Punjab. The non-experimental descriptive research design was followed and 125 students were selected as study subjects with total enumerative sampling technique. Modified adolescent peer relation instrument were used to assess the prevalence of bullying among senior secondary students. The study was concluded in the month of September. The study findings reveal that majority of students have mild form of bullying those, who have excellent level of marks in their academic performance with mean and standard deviation of 28.54+8.331.

Keywords: Bullying, academic Performance, Senior Secondary Students.

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INTRODUCTION

Better education is very necessary for all to go ahead in life and get success. If develops confidence and helps to build the personality of a person. School education, plays a great role in everyone's life. The whole education has been divided into three divisions such as primary, secondary and higher education, Primary education prepares the base, secondary education prepares the path for further study and higher secondary education prepares the ultimate path of the further and whole life.

Our good or bad education decides which type of person would in future. Academic achievement can be obtained through students efforts by learning and study in their school or college. There is a deep connection between education and productively and in this age where there is more competition at every turn. It is fact well known that more the education have, better would by economic performance.

Behavior means the way that you act or behave with other while talking. Behavior among students means stimulus driven responses that occur specifically with the college, classroom or how students are acting in the classroom in response to what is going on or present around them. Good behavior and discipline in schools is crucial if children are to learn and reach thin full potential. We are committed to improving behavior and discipline in schools because know the effect of misbehavior that can lost learning time and harm the life chances of young people that's why we their it is so

important to tackle poor behavior so teachers are able to provide high quality teaching to all.

Bullying is a behavioral phenomenon or situation which is characterized by intentional, verbal or physical abuse by one or more students against peers. This phenomenon is a form of violence that is quickly growing in the world. Bullying is a case in which one individual is picked as the target of repeat aggression by one or others.

Bullying is a major problem around the globe. Bullying is observed across race, gender, ethnicity, and socioeconomic status. It is prevalent in all grades and all schools and can be mild, moderate, or even severe. Bullying has been the focus of recent international research. The estimated prevalence of bullying usually depends on how bullying is perceived and who reports the incidence. Teachers and parents frequently report fewer cases of bullying behaviors than children and young people.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A descriptive study was done to access the bullying and its impact on the psycho social well-being among high school students of Udupi district, Karnataka. A total of 460 students were selected through simple random sampling between the age group of 13-17 years. Bullying scale was used to explore bullying and psychosocial will being scale. The result showed that mean and Standard deviation bully behaviour was found to be higher compare to fight and victim 7.31 (SD = 5.65) they conduced that

bullying is significantly associated gender and area of residence whereas; psycho social will being is significantly associated with family monthly income.

A descriptive study was done to access the prevalence and attitude of bullying behaviour among school children in selected schools at Bangalore. A structured interview schedule and Likert scale was used to access the prevalence and attitude and the sample was used on 120 children of age between 8 to 15 years in selected school using convenient sampling techniques. The results indicated that majority 66.7% had moderate prevalence rate of bullying and 31.7% had low level prevalence of bullying behaviour and only 1.7% had high level prevalence of bullying behaviour among school children. They concluded that self- instructional module were provided to create awarance among teachers regarding bullying behaviour and its prevention.

A cross sectional study was done to access the Bullying behaviour and psychosocial health among school students of Pythan Municipality. The sample was 8th, 9th and 10th grade student of Pythan Municipality. A total of 405 students responded to the structured self-administered Questionnaire. Descriptive and inferential statics were used for analyses. The result of this study showed that higher prevalence bullying (55.8 %) among Students of relativity advantaged were as victims (64.86 %-) belongs to disadvantaged ganagatis. Student who bully were found more in grade 8th and 10th while the list of the student grade 9th were more victim. The overall prevalence is 69.14%

A described study was conducted to access the impact of school bulling on students. Academic Achievement from Teachers point of view in Jordan Ian schools. The sample size consisted of 200 teachers selected from different Schools. The study used a descriptive analytical Methodology a self-administrative questionnaire was designed according to search objective and hypotheses and distributed over research sample subject. The

research result indicated that School Bullying exists in all school regardless if they are governmental or private ones. The Study concluded that school bullying affect students’ academic Achievement either victims or the bullies.

A descriptive study was done to access the extent of bullying among school students, The ruvanthampuram, Kerala. The sample for the present study was selected from different schools, which consist of 300 boys & 300 girls with a total sample of 600 school students. The main research tool used for the study bullying questionnaire constructed for the present study. Data was collected from the students in their respective classrooms, which were then scored, coded & than analysed. The statistical techniques used are descriptive statistics namely frequency& percentage. The result showed that 10% of the study are not safe in their school. It was found that 53.5% of the students in the study have experienced bullying during the past 4 weeks. The study concluded that, there is prevalence of bullying behaviours among school students in Kerala.

Methodology

Socio-demographic data consists of personal information of the subjects that include Age, gender, Stream, Religion, Type of Family, Income, Birth order, Number of Siblings, School Attendance, Previous Year of Result. The data collection for the study was carried out in the month of May2023.Non-probability total enumerative sampling technique was used to select 125 Students who were studying in selected school. Researcher first introduced herself to the respondents and explained the purpose of study. Study procedure was explained to the study subjects and a written consent was obtained. The tool was administered to the study subjects. They were assured that their response would be kept confidential and would be used only for research purpose. All subject took 15-20 minutes to fill up the research tool.

SAMPLE CHARACTERISTICS OF STUDY SUBJECTS

Table -1: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Sample Characteristic

N=125

Variables	n	%
1. Age (In Years)		
(a) 15	29	23.2
(b) 16	55	44.0
(c) 17	38	30.4
(d) 18	03	2.4
2. Gender		
(a) Male	75	60
(b) Female	50	40
3. Stream		
(a) Medical	26	20.8
(b) Non - Medical	38	30.4
(c) Commerce	40	32.0
(d) Arts	21	16.8

4. Religion		
(a) Sikh	82	65.6
(b) Hindu	43	34.4
5. Type of Family		
(a) Nuclear	67	53.6
(b) Joint	57	45.6
(c) Extended	1	0.8
6. Income		
(a) 10,000 - 20,000/-	23	18.4
(b) 20,001 - 30,000/-	24	19.2
(c) 30,001 - 40,000/-	30	24.0
(d) Above 40,000/-	48	38.4
Variables	N	%
7. Birth Order		
(a) First	67	53.6
(b) Second	51	40.8
(c) Third	7	5.6
8. No. of Siblings		
(a) Single Child	13	10.4
(b) One Sibling	53	42.4
(c) Two Sibling	46	36.8
(d) More than two	13	10.4
9. School Attendance		
(a) 70 - 100%	115	92.0
(b) 50 - 70%	9	7.2
(c) Below 50%	1	0.8

Table 1 and shows the frequency and percentage distribution of sample characteristics. According to **age (in years)**, little less than one fifth (23.2%) were belonged to 15 years followed by little more than two fifth (44%) were belonged to 16 years whereas little less than one-third (30.4%) were belonged to 17 years and the rest (2.4%) were belonged to 18 years. According to **gender**, three fifth (60%) were males and two fifth (40%) were females. According to **stream**, one fifth (20.8%) were having medical followed by little less than one third (30.4%) were having non- medical whereas little less than one third (32.0%) were having commerce and rest (16.8%) were having arts. According to **religion**, little less than two-third (65.6%) were belonged to sikh religion whereas remaining little more than one third (34.4%) were hindu. According to **type of family**, little more than half (53.6%) hailed from nuclear family whereas little less than half (45.6%) hailed from joint family and rest (0.8%) belonged to extended family. According to **income** little less than one fifth (18.4% and 19.2%) were having income 10,000- 20,000 and 20,001-30,000 respectively, followed by little less than one fourth (24%) were having income of 30,001-40,000/- and rest (38.4%) were having income of above 40,000/-. According to **birth order**, more than half (53.6%) were first child whereas two fifth (40.8%) were second child and rest (5.6%) were third child of their house. According to **no of siblings**, same no one-tenth (10.4%) were single child and more than two respectively followed by little more than two fifth (42.4%) were having one sibling and rest (36.8%) were having two siblings. According to school **school attendance**, maximum student, (92.0%) were having 70-100% school attendance followed by few (7.2%) were having 50-70% school attendance and rest (0.8%) were having below 50% school attendance.

Hence, it is concluded that out of 125 students, maximum were belong to 16 years, majority were males. Maximum were commerce student belong to sikh religion and having nuclear family, maximum have income above 40,000/- and were first child also having single sibling, maximum student were 70-100% school attendance.

Figure 1(a): Percentage distribution of senior secondary students according to age (in year).

Figure 1(b): Percentage distribution of senior secondary students according to gender.

Figure 1(c): Percentage distribution of senior secondary students according to stream.

Figure 1(d): Percentage distribution of senior secondary students according to religion.

Figure 1(e): Percentage distribution of senior secondary students according to type of family.

Figure 1(f): Percentage distribution of senior secondary students according to income.

Figure 1(g): Percentage distribution of senior secondary students according to Birth order.

Figure 1(h): Percentage distribution of senior secondary students according to No. of siblings.

Figure 1(i): Percentage distribution of senior secondary students according to school attendance.

OBJECTIVE WISE ANALYSIS

OBJECTIVE-1 To assess the prevalence of bullying and its impact on academic performance among senior secondary students studying in Khalsa College Public School, Amritsar.

Table 2(a): Frequency and percentage distribution of Senior Secondary Student according to the level of bullying.

Level of MAPRI Score	N	%	Mean + SD
Mild (1-36)	104	83.2	
Moderate (37-72)	21	16.8	28.54 + 8.3
Severe (72-108)	0	0	

Table 2(a) and fig 5 depicts Frequency and percentage distribution of Senior Secondary Student according to the level of bullying. It shows that majority of students experienced Mild level of bullying (83.2) whereas 16.8% students experienced moderate level of bullying. Hence, it can be said that most of the students are experiencing mild level of bullying.

Figure 2: Percentage distribution of Senior Secondary Student according to the level of bullying.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study concluded that majority of students have mild level of bullying those who have excellent level of marks in their academic performances.

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